

Society for Mycotoxin Research
Gesellschaft für Mykotoxinforschung e.V.

45th Mycotoxin Workshop

Book of Abstract

© Wien Tourismus

Local organisers:
Doris Marko, Elisabeth Varga

vetmeduni

P42 – Mycotoxin contamination of cereal-based gluten-free food

Ljilja Torovic^{1,2}, Gordana Milojevic Miodragovic², Sanja Bijelovic^{2,3}

¹Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

²Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Serbia

³Department of Hygiene, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

If present in food, mycotoxins (fungal toxins) could pose human health risk. Aflatoxins (AFs), ochratoxin A (OTA), zearalenone (ZEA), deoxynivalenol (DON) and fumonisins (FUM) are well known food contaminants, all regulated by the EU law [1]. A noticeable diversification of the assortment of gluten free foods intended to people with celiac disease has recently been observed. Celiac disease is a systemic, autoimmune disease that occurs in about 1% of the population. Genetically predisposed individuals exhibit a lifelong intolerance to gluten, as dietary intake of gluten leads to inflammatory changes in the lining of the small intestine. These individuals need to avoid gluten in their diet, which in practice means avoidance of wheat, barley, rye (and oat) [2].

The objective of the study was to perceive the extent of mycotoxin contamination of cereal-derived gluten-free food available on the Serbian market. A total of 60 samples, including flour, pasta, bread, cake and snack products, all marked with a crossed grain symbol or “gluten free” wording, was purchased in supermarkets. Determination of each mycotoxin was performed using immuno-affinity columns with specific antibodies for the clean-up of sample extracts and quantification by high performance liquid chromatography with ultraviolet (DON) or fluorescence detection (OTA, ZEA) using o-phthalaldehyde precolumn derivatization (FB1, FB2) or UV postcolumn derivatization (AFs). All methods were validated and accredited according to the standard ISO 17025.

The study revealed the dominant presence of OTA, in 28.3% of the samples in their entirety, and specifically in 40.0, 36.4, 33.3, 22.2 and 18.8% of the cake, flour, pasta, bread and snack samples, respectively. OTA was the only mycotoxin found in concentrations exceeding the maximum level set for cereal products (2 µg/kg): 6.44 and 5.03 µg/kg, in one pasta (based on rice, corn, millet and buckwheat) and one snack (corn, rice, millet) sample, respectively. It was interesting to note that all mycotoxins except AFs achieved maximum concentrations in pasta samples (ZEA 7.85, DON 389.6, FUM 429.5 µg/kg), while the highest AFs level (0.46 µg/kg) was recorded in bread and snack samples. However, mean concentrations were rather low: below 0.1 and 2 µg/kg for AFs and ZEA, respectively, while mean levels of OTA, DON and FUM all reached maximum in pasta samples, at 0.65, 56.6 and 64.7 µg/kg, respectively. Thirteen out of 60 samples showed multi-mycotoxin occurrence: 9 contained mycotoxins from two classes (two thirds of them being AFs+OTA combination), 3 (bread, cake and snack) had three types of mycotoxins (AFs+OTA+DON or AFs+OTA+FUM), whereas 1 sample exhibited simultaneous presence of OTA, ZEA, DON and FUM. It was observed that vast majority of these samples was based on corn, being their only or principal ingredient.

The study findings indicate that activities directed towards protection of public health should be carefully considered.

[1] European Commission. Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/915 of 25 April 2023 on maximum levels for certain contaminants in food and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006. Off. J. EU 2023, L119, 103–157.

[2] Celiac disease foundation. What is celiac disease? Retrieved from: <https://celiac.org/about-celiac-disease/what-is-celiac-disease/> (accessed 29 February 2024).